

SAR Imaging Using WiMAX OFDM PHY

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Abstract—Modern communication systems provide myriad opportunities for passive radar applications. Understanding the structure and potential of these signals becomes critical in the design and concept development process of passive radar systems. Although research exists for passive coherent target location, there is much to be explored in the passive radar imaging realm using signals of opportunity. This paper presents an evaluation of the IEEE 802.16-2009 WiMAX OFDM physical layer as a potential signal for a passive imaging radar system. The use of OFDM signals in radar imaging is explored and basic WiMAX imaging properties are discussed.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the key advantages of passive radar is the ability to use “off-platform” signals of opportunity as the illumination source. Available signal types include radio, television, and cellular broadcasts, whose content, frequency, and modulation characteristics vary worldwide. The recent IEEE 802.16-2009 standard defines an orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) broadband signal commonly referred to as WiMAX. The potential worldwide deployment of WiMAX makes it an attractive signal of opportunity for passive radar. This paper introduces the WiMAX OFDM physical (PHY) layer as a potential signal for radar imaging within the passive radar construct. Recovery of the scene reflectivity function is shown to be a match filter process using the WiMAX OFDM data.

Prior OFDM radar work is briefly introduced in the next section. Section III develops the range profile solution using OFDM signals in a monostatic setup while WiMAX-specific considerations are discussed in Section IV. Section V shows simulation results.

II. BACKGROUND

An OFDM signal transmits coded information in multiple carrier channels simultaneously. A pre-determined bandwidth is partitioned into N subcarriers, each a harmonic of the lowest frequency in the band. In this sense, all subcarriers are mutually orthogonal. The orthogonality allows for close spreading of the data in frequency with minimum interference between them, resulting in a more efficient use of the allocated bandwidth [1].

Although the use of OFDM in communications is widespread, there has been limited research in OFDM for radar applications. OFDM as a radar waveform was formally evaluated by Levanon in [10] [9]. Despite OFDM usability, linear frequency modulation (LFM) has been the waveform of preference for radar imaging due to its range compression and baseband sampling properties.

Modern OFDM radar research can be found in recent literature. Falcone and Chetty present OFDM radar detection and tracking work in [4] and [2] respectively. Imaging radar concepts using ultra-wideband OFDM are proposed by Garmatyuk in [6] and [5], while Sturm obtains range profile information using an OFDM waveform in both simulation and experimental setups [13], [14]. Gutierrez evaluated the bistatic ambiguity function properties of the WiMAX signal where favorable wide-angle bistatic characteristics are observed [7]. In this paper, we investigate the processing required to recover the scene reflectivity function from OFDM WiMAX radar signals.

III. RADAR IMAGING USING OFDM

The goal of imaging radar is to obtain an estimate of the two-dimensional scene reflectivity function. We are interested in producing phase history data to assemble a portion of the scene reflectivity spectrum. When using linear frequency modulation (LFM), low-pass filtering after the *dechirp* process directly transduces spatial frequency phase histories [8]. In contrast, demodulating and filtering a continuous wave (CW) pulse results in the convolution of the scene reflectivity function with the system point spread function (PSF). One can think of an OFDM broadcast as the simultaneous transmission of multiple CW pulses over a given frequency band. We show that for OFDM signals, phase histories are obtained by a match filtering process using the modulation data. The OFDM range profile solution is initially developed within the monostatic radar construct. The bistatic model is deferred to future work.

In communications, the OFDM waveform generation begins with a randomized set of data bits modulated using BPSK, QPSK, or QAM modulations, producing complex data d_n . The desired signal bandwidth B is divided into N subcarriers evenly spaced in frequency by:

Fig. 1: WiMAX time domain symbol model.

Fig. 2: Time domain signal assembly. Symbols in time domain are the linear superposition of N modulated subcarriers.

$$\Delta f = \frac{B}{N} \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of the available subcarriers and the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) length. Note the effective signal bandwidth is defined by $B_{eff} = 1/T_s = \Delta f$. Each n th subcarrier is modulated with the amplitude and phase of a particular data d_n . All subcarriers are subsequently assembled in parallel through an inverse DFT operation before transmission. Figure 1 shows a simplified model of the OFDM wave generating process. The time-domain signal becomes a sequence of symbols, each a linear superposition of the N -modulated subcarriers as depicted in Figure 2. The communication symbol duration is defined by $T_s = 1/\Delta f$.

For one communication symbol, the OFDM transmitted signal voltage to the antenna is modelled in complex form as [3]:

$$s(t) = e^{jw_0 t} \sum_{n=-N/2}^{N/2} d_n e^{jn\Delta w t}, \quad 0 \leq t < T_s \quad (2)$$

where w_0 is the carrier frequency in radians/sec, d_n is the complex data to be transmitted on the n th subcarrier, and Δw is the subcarrier frequency spacing in radians per second. Assuming interference-free channels and known data d_n , the received signal from a single pulse interacting with a ground patch of infinite scatterers in complex form is [8]:

$$s_{r0}(t) = A_0 \int_{u_a}^{u_b} g(u) e^{jw_0(t-\tau_0-\tau_u)} \sum_{n=-N/2}^{N/2} d_n e^{jn\Delta w(t-\tau_0-\tau_u)} du \quad (3)$$

where A_0 is the gain associated with the radar equation, $g(u)$ is the reflectivity density as a function of slant range u , the limits u_a and u_b represent the near and far ranges respectively, τ_0 is the two-way delay associated with the range to scene center, and τ_u is the two-way delay associated with slant range u . It can be shown that after the return signal is mixed with the in-phase and quadrature phase of the signal carrier and low-pass filtered, the ideal resultant baseband signal becomes:

$$s_r(t) = \frac{A_0}{2} \int_{u_a}^{u_b} g(u) e^{-jw_0 \tau_u} \sum_{n=-N/2}^{N/2} d_n e^{jn\Delta w(t-\tau_0-\tau_u)} du \quad (4)$$

Bringing the carrier integral term inside the summation and rearranging yields:

$$s_r(t) = \frac{A_0}{2} \sum_{n=-N/2}^{N/2} d_n e^{jn\Delta w(t-\tau_0)} \int_{u_a}^{u_b} g(u) e^{-j(w_0+n\Delta w)\tau_u} du \quad (5)$$

Assuming a monostatic configuration, $\tau_u = 2u/c$, and defining a spatial frequency variable as:

$$k_n = \frac{2}{c}(w_0 + n\Delta w) \quad (6)$$

simplifies (5) to:

$$s_r(t) = \frac{A_0}{2} \sum_{n=-N/2}^{N/2} \left[d_n e^{jn\Delta w(t-\tau_0)} \int_{u_a}^{u_b} g(u) e^{-jk_n u} du \right] \quad (7)$$

Note that similar to the LFM case [8], the integral in (7) is a Fourier transform over the range of discrete spatial frequencies:

$$\frac{2}{c}(w_0 - \frac{N}{2}\Delta w) \leq k_n \leq \frac{2}{c}(w_0 + \frac{N}{2}\Delta w) \quad (8)$$

or in terms of signal bandwidth:

$$\frac{2}{c}(w_0 - \pi B) \leq k_n \leq \frac{2}{c}(w_0 + \pi B) \quad (9)$$

Letting:

$$\int_{u_a}^{u_b} g(u)e^{-jk_n u} du = G[k_n] \quad (10)$$

leads to:

$$s_r(t) = \frac{A_0}{2} \sum_{n=-N/2}^{N/2} d_n G[k_n] e^{-jn\Delta w\tau_0} e^{jn\Delta w t} \quad (11)$$

Let A_n be the n th coefficient defined by:

$$A_n = \frac{A_0}{2} d_n G[k_n] e^{-jn\Delta w\tau_0} \quad (12)$$

then (11) becomes:

$$s_r(t) = \sum_{n=-N/2}^{N/2} A_n e^{jn\Delta w t} \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) is the Fourier series representation of the received signal for which coefficients are determined by:

$$A_n = \frac{1}{T_s} \int_0^{T_s} s_r(t) e^{-jn\Delta w t} dt \quad (14)$$

Note that the integral in (14) is the Fourier transform S_n of the received signal $s_r(t)$ for all integers n of which only N carriers carry signal energy. Merging (14) and (12), and solving for $G[k_n]$ yields:

$$G[k_n] = \frac{2S_n e^{jn\Delta w\tau_0}}{A_0 T_s d_n} = \frac{K_n S_n}{d_n} \quad (15)$$

for all n such that $d_n \neq 0$ and where $K_n = 2e^{jn\Delta w\tau_0}/(A_0 T_s)$. Multiplying the numerator and the denominator by the conjugate of d_n results in:

$$G[k_n] = \frac{K_n}{|d_n|^2} (S_n d_n^*) \quad (16)$$

Equation (16) reveals a match filter operation where the return signal is matched with the complex subcarrier modulation d_n in frequency domain. In the SAR context, the two-dimensional scene phase history is assembled on a pulse-by-pulse basis:

$$\Phi(k_n, p) = G[k_n, p] \quad (17)$$

where p is the pulse number. Then, any imaging technique such as the polar reformatting algorithm or convolution backprojection may be employed to recover an image—the estimate of scene reflectivity map. Note that (16) is not WiMAX exclusive; the general form applies to any OFDM signal.

In summary, the process to obtain phase histories on a pulse-by-pulse-basis using OFDM is 1) Fourier transform the return signal, and 2) multiply in frequency domain by the

Fig. 3: Subcarrier allocation in frequency domain.

conjugate of the complex modulation data. A one-dimensional range profile can be obtained from any pulse by applying the inverse Fourier transform to the match filter output over the applicable spatial frequencies k_n .

The spatial frequency support in (9) defines a monostatic downrange (y) resolution of:

$$\rho_y = \frac{c}{2B} \quad (18)$$

and imaging range dimension of:

$$D_y = N \frac{c}{2B} \quad (19)$$

It is worthwhile to provide a brief discussion on similarities and differences of OFDM and LFM waveforms within the imaging domain. The resolution obtainable using both waveforms is directly related to the signal bandwidth with a range compression factor. The pulse compression in LFM has the advantage of producing a lower bandwidth baseband, relaxing the sampling criteria but only in those cases where the pulse length is much shorter than the illuminated patch [8], [12]. When the length of the scene of interest is larger than the LFM pulse, match filtering is generally required. Two immediate advantages of OFDM over LFM are the absence of the residual video phase error and range-Doppler decoupling in the ambiguity function.

IV. 802.16-2009, WiMAX

Employing signals of opportunity for radar imaging requires full understanding of the candidate waveform. This section provides a brief introduction to the WiMAX signal structure before and after transmission. For a thorough description, the reader is referred to the IEEE 802.16-2009 documentation [3].

The *Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access* or WiMAX, is a broadband wireless networking standard which aims to address interoperability across IEEE 802.16-2009 standard based products [3]. As of February 2011, there are 582 fixed and mobile WiMAX deployments in 149 countries [15]. Worldwide deployment of WiMAX systems provides unique opportunities for emerging passive radar applications. Operating in the frequency band between 2 and 11 GHz,

Fig. 4: Transmitted symbol. Cyclic prefix appended at beginning is a replica of the end of the symbol.

Fig. 5: Down link subframe assembly. Each time block represents a symbol.

WiMAX systems can provide 5 to 10 km of service area with a maximum data rate of 70 Mbps in a scalable 20 MHz channel [11].

The 802.16-2009 standard defines three physical layer configurations: single carrier, 256-point OFDM, and OFDMA with up to 2048 subcarriers. For this paper, only the 256-point (256 subcarriers) OFDM PHY is considered. Figure 3 shows a graphical representation of the subcarrier structure in the frequency domain. Of the 256 subcarriers, 192 are used for data, 8 are used for pilot codes, and 55 are used for guard bands. The 8 pilot bits are equally spaced throughout the bandwidth and are appended to all data symbols after the preamble for channel condition estimation. The DC subcarrier is always null.

Once transformed to time domain through the inverse DFT operation, a replica of a fraction of the symbol is appended to the beginning to avoid inter-symbol interference (ISI) due to multipath. This replica is defined as the cyclic prefix (CP) with time duration of T_g as shown in Figure 4.

The data symbols are transmitted in time domain using a predefined frame structure. Each frame consists of a downlink (DL) subframe and an uplink (UL) subframe. For our radar application, only the DL subframe is considered. Figure 5 shows the DL general structure. The DL preamble consists of either one or two symbols and is used for initial ranging and synchronization. The preamble data is subcarrier dependent, always employs the same bit sequence, and is “boosted” 3dB higher in amplitude relative to the rest of the data symbols. The frame carrier heading (FCH) symbol contains subcarrier mapping information for the entire subframe. Every subframe carries all the necessary details (frame length, number of

Fig. 6: Three actual time-domain WiMAX frames: 5MHz bandwidth over a 5.1GHz carrier

symbols, number of preambles, etc.) for signal processing at the communications receiver. Figure 6 shows three DL subframes from a real WiMAX signal over a 5.1 GHz carrier where the preamble symbols are clearly seen at the beginning of each pulse. The selective frequency fading is due to multipath interference; typically corrected through equalization filters. No UL subframes were transmitted between DL subframes.

WiMAX networks are designed to be deployed over large urban and rural areas through the use of tower mounted antennas using line-of-sight (LOS) and non-LOS transmissions. As such, the transmitter locations are fixed and known. The transmitter-target path and incident angle will always be constant. Phase histories will then depend mostly on receiver location, analogous to monostatic configurations.

Table I defines several WiMAX parameters related to radar imaging. Note that WiMAX has bandwidth for range resolution and PRF for cross range resolution—the basic elements of radar imaging processing. The ratio of the signal bandwidth to the operating frequencies is less than 1%; small enough to be considered narrow-band for Doppler and signal processing purposes. Analogous to the LFM signal, there is a pulse compression factor inherent in the pulse. Recall the effective bandwidth of the pulse is Δf , leading to an effective

TABLE I: Radar parameters for WiMAX signal.

Parameter	Value
Base station tx power	85 dBm
Operating frequency	2-11 GHz
PRF (DL frame rate)	50-400 Hz
Pulse width (per symbol)	0.04-0.7 μ s
Bandwidth B	1.25-20 MHz
Process sampling frequency f_s	1.4-23 MHz
Range resolution	7.5-120 m
Unambiguous range	375-3000 Km

Fig. 7: Simulation core concept.

resolution of $c/2\Delta f$. The pulse compression factor can be easily determined by:

$$\frac{\rho_{eff}}{\rho_y} = \frac{c/2\Delta f}{c/2B} = \frac{cN/2B}{c/2B} \approx N \quad (20)$$

The range compression value is approximate because the use of the cyclic prefix will slightly reduce the effective bandwidth.

The way the WiMAX signal is built introduces specific challenges for SAR signal processing. Every symbol in the WiMAX transmission is composed of a specific number of subcarriers. For example, of the 256 defined subcarriers in the bandwidth, only 200 contain data. Of those 200 subcarriers, the preamble symbols only use even subcarriers in multiples of 2 or multiples of 4, but always producing 256 time samples from the IFFT process. Data subcarriers would probably use most if not all the 200 subcarriers all the time. Multiple symbols of a single DL subframe (or a single “pulse”) may have to be individually and coherently processed to fill the spatial frequency domain raster before imaging. Another consideration is the 20 MHz maximum bandwidth of the WiMAX pulse; small when compared to the bandwidth used in legacy SAR systems. This bandwidth also varies from pulse to pulse in response to channel conditions. The resolution of a WiMAX imaging system will be limited, variable, and for most cases unpredictable. Lastly, tower transmissions are typically *sectorized*, transmitting different data over the same frequency bands in different directions. Although difficult, these challenges are not impossible to overcome. The ability to use OFDM signals of opportunity for radar imaging certainly outweighs the limitations of a practical solution.

V. SIMULATED SAR IMAGERY

A simulation platform was developed for the analysis of OFDM SAR imagery. The simulation validates the mathematical concept developed in section III through the modelling of signal generation, transmission, reception, and processing of a monostatic OFDM SAR system. Each pulse return is converted to phase histories using (16). Figure 7 shows a diagram of the simulation concept. After phase

Fig. 8: Simulation point target scene (left) and its spotlight SAR image (right) using a 100 MHz OFDM signal over a 1 GHz carrier. Simulated collection from a 6-degree azimuth swath sampled at 0.02-degree intervals. Down range resolution: 1.5m, Cross range resolution: 1.4 m

Fig. 9: Simulated spotlight SAR image of target scene from a 256-carrier (left) and a 200-carrier (right) WiMAX signal over a 1 GHz carrier, $B=20$ MHz. Simulated collection from a 6-degree azimuth swath sampled at 0.02-degree intervals. Down range resolution ≈ 7.5 m, Cross range resolution = 1.4 m

histories for all pulses are obtained, a SAR image is produced using a two-dimensional Fourier transform. The resulting images shown are free from pre-filtering windows and/or polar reformatting processing.

Figure 8 shows the discrete point target scene employed and its SAR image representation using a 100 MHz bandwidth OFDM signal over a 1 GHz carrier. The synthetic aperture was obtained from a simulated monostatic level collection using 0.02-degree samples over a 6-degree azimuth broadside swath. The figure shows that range compression using (16) is possible and the 1.5-meter resolution correctly corresponds to the signal bandwidth $B = 100\text{MHz}$.

Figure 9 shows two SAR images using a simulated 20 MHz WiMAX signal. The left image shows the limited range resolution (7.5 meters) when using all 256

Fig. 10: Simulated PFA image of a single point target using 20MHz preamble symbols P1 (left) and P2 (right). Simulated collection from a 6-degree azimuth swath sampled at 0.02-degree intervals. Down range resolution $\approx 7.5\text{m}$, Cross range resolution = 1.4 m

available subcarriers. Note that the bottom two targets are undistinguishable. The right image shows further degradation when guard bands are employed per IEEE 802.16 specifications (see Figure 3); this is the best range resolution attainable using a single receiver and traditional SAR processing techniques. Practical resolution levels could be possible for example, through multi-receiver exploitation.

In a passive radar scenario, one may not have access to the transmitted data d_n for match filtering. However, the preamble data are always known in accordance with implementation standards. Two of the WiMAX OFDM PHY preamble symbols carry data only over certain subcarrier intervals in the DL: P1 uses 50 subcarriers and P2 uses 100 subcarriers. The number of spatial frequency samples will be the number of subcarriers employed. As such, the preamble undersamples the spectrum, reducing the imaging area. Figure 10 shows the aliasing when WiMAX preambles are used for a single point scatterer in the scene center. Larger imaging areas would require the augmentation of the samples using additional data symbols from the same DL burst.

VI. CONCLUSION

The potential of WiMAX as signal of opportunity for radar imaging is evaluated. It is shown that WiMAX has pulse compression properties, and allows for the deconvolution of the scene reflectivity function using a simple match filter operation. Simulated SAR imagery validates the phase history collection process using OFDM and demonstrates basic WiMAX imaging capabilities. WiMAX is found to have limited range resolution which could be improved through alternative processing and multi-receiver approaches. The direct use of the WiMAX preambles results in range profile aliasing which would require advanced techniques for

practical use.

Many aspects of the proposed system still require in-depth understanding. Future research should focus on analysis of OFDM imaging properties, modelling bistatic and multistatic collections, and the use of advanced SAR image processing techniques.

The complexity of WiMAX along with the inherent complexities of the passive radar creates a formidable engineering challenge. Nevertheless, the world-wide deployment of WiMAX networks offers a unique opportunity of global reach and motivates further research.

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